

Business Matching Model for Small and Medium Enterprises

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Abstract

Along with the economic growth in the industrial sector, MSMEs, and startups, the creative economy has now developed in Indonesia, especially in the city of Bandung. However, there are problems in developing the creative industry in Bandung; namely: there is no accurate data about the picture of the sector, MSMEs, and creative economy. This research is used qualitative research. The method of data analysis uses deductive methods, which are methods used in discussions, departing from knowledge of a general nature and then assessing something of a unique character. The general understanding in this study refers to the analysis of literature on business matching, fair trade, fair show/expo, and related about inventase and capital. Thus, after departing from the general concept that has been generalized, then interpreted with existing theories and reference sources, the result is strategic business matching models to bring inventiveness that can be implemented in Bandung.

Keywords: *Business Matching, MSMEs, Start-Ups, Creative Industries.*

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia had experienced an economic crisis that caused the collapse of the national economy. The majority of large-scale businesses experienced a slump and even threatened the company's business activities in 2008. When Indonesia's economic condition has not recovered, Indonesia again faced the entanglement of the financial crisis due to the Covid-19 Pandemic in 2000. The Covid-19 pandemic has impacted large-scale business processes in various sectors. However, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) were able to survive and become economic restorers amid the downturn caused by the monetary crisis in different economic sectors (Sudarsono, 2009; Kurniadi in Trehan & Trehan, 2022).

The role of MSMEs is significant in providing jobs and producing helpful output people. The development of small businesses contributes to absorbing labor and providing flexibility and innovation needs in the economy (Kurniadi in Trehan & Trehan, 2022).

After passing through the monetary crisis, MSMEs made a significant contribution to Indonesia's gross domestic product in 2015 of 61.41%, with a labor absorption of 96.71%. Until 2017, the Indonesian economy, based on the amount of Gross Domestic Product based on prevailing prices, reached Rp3,502.3 trillion and, based on constant prices in 2010, reached Rp2,551.5 trillion. In the third quarter of 2017, against the third quarter of 2016 (yon-y), Indonesia's economy grew by 5.06%. All components growth, where the highest growth was achieved by the Export Component of Goods and Services at 17.27%—followed by the Gross Fixed Capital Formation Component at 7.11%. The

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Expenditure Component of Non-Profit Institutions Serving Households at 6.01%, the Household Consumption Expenditure Component at 4.93%, and the Government Consumption Expenditure Component at 3.46% (BPS, 2017).

Similarly, economic growth in the city of Bandung has industrial potential, both large, medium, small, and micro industries. There are ten significant industries in 2021 in Bandung and 825 unit medium industries (Kurniadi & Ibrahim, 2021). Table 1 explains the potential of the industrial sector in the city of Bandung.

Table 1. Industrial Sector Potential in Bandung City 2021

No.	Criterion	Business Unit	Workforce
1	Large Industry	10	857
2	Medium Industry	825	23.321
3	Formal Small Industry	2.770	43.692
4	Non-Formal Small Industries	12.279	43.326

Source: Research Results (2021)

Furthermore, in the MSME sector, Bandung city continues to develop every year to become a sector that improves the economy, as described in Tabel 2 (Kurniadi & Ibrahim, 2021).

Table 2. Number of MSMEs in Bandung City in 2016-2021

No.	Business Type	Year					
		2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	Micro	3,649	3,827	3,921	4,115	4,301	4,527
2	Small	301	325	337	357	327	390
3	Intermediate	271	273	273	274	276	281
Total		4221	4425	4531	4746	4904	5198

Source: Research Results (2021)

The high growth shows that Bandung City is one of the cities with the growing economic growth of MSMEs. Along with the increase in MSME growth, there is a push to increase competitiveness through technical support. However, on the other hand, technology demands fundamental changes to behavior patterns. Currently, an employee can do his job by monitoring or monitoring from a computer remotely controlled. A programmer does not even have an office to work in daily because they can work anywhere with technological devices like laptops, computers, and software that support them. Of course, this change will encourage people to build their own companies. Thus, startups become a business solution that can be worked on (Baluch et al., 2015). The development of startups in Indonesia is high-speed. According to techno ozone, at least currently, there are 2500 local startups in Indonesia and Bandung, which are known as creative cities and has the potential to become an area that will be filled with the pace of startup growth (Darmansyah, 2015; Baluch et al., 2015).

Along with the economy's growth in the industrial sector, MSMEs, and startups, the creative economy has now developed in Indonesia. The Ministry of Trade introduced the creative economy, Industry, and Ministry of Tourism through the Indonesia Design Power program 2006-2010. Any 16 sub-sectors in the Creative Industry: fashion, crafts, culinary, publishing and printing, design, art, and antique markets, music, photography, television and radio, architecture, advertising, computer services, and software, research, and development, interactive games, performing arts, film, and video.

Source: Research Results (2021)

Figure 1. Business Actors in the Creative Industry sector of Bandung City 2021

The number of business actors who participated in the creative industry survey in the city of Bandung netted as many as 2357 people. The fashion sub-sector appears dominant with 1244 people and a percentage of 52.78%. Fashion is a creative activity that high imagination. So, the craft sector is in second place after a fashion. Based on survey calculations, 395 craft business actors have a percentage rate of 16.76%. There is a culinary sub-sector in the third place, with the number of culinary business actors recorded at 381 people or 16.16%.

Three sectors increase the attractiveness of Bandung City. Especially for investors or investors. It is natural considering that products from the three sub-sectors are a favorite target for tourists visiting Kota Bandung. When summed up, the three sub-sectors above (fashion, crafts, and culinary) contributed 85.70% of business actors from all creative eco-sectors in the Bandung City.

Bandung City is an important city for business activity in Indonesia as a growth center focusing on economic growth in various sectors. However, some things are problems that are often not planned carefully, such as;

- a. There is no accurate and detailed data on the overall economic picture covering industry, MSMEs, Creative Economy, and new businesses/businesses growing both in technology (startup) and non-technology.
- b. Explain at point a is a reference for the preparation of business matching planning in Kota Bandung and is the initial and fundamental data in determining business matching planning in Bandung city.

The preparation of models or business matching planning for Bandung is a form of a vision Bandung, namely the realization of Bandung, superior, comfortable, and prosperous. Prosperity for the people of Bandung, including for business actors in Bandung, through strategic steps, one of which is a business collaboration or known as business matching.

Business matching and adequate information supplies related to business needs, such as raw material needs, business partners, and the like, facilitate the development of interrelationships between businesses. Also increasingly needed in the era of global trade. Because the market has developed in a broader scope and also because of the limitations of the supply chain network that leads to market uncertainty (market) which is often called the short supply chain (Yeow, 2000).

The primary purpose of business matching activities is to create business relationships between two or more parties to build sustainable business strength and the life span of the company/business to last longer. The form of business matching can be an expo activity or a trade show. The expo is held so that companies from specific industries can showcase and demonstrate their products and services, and businesses can learn about competitors' activities and follow trends to find new opportunities (Aditya, 2014).

Some trade shows or expos that have been held in the city of Bandung are usually open to the public. In contrast, others can only be attended by company representatives, business actors such as creative economy actors, and MSMEs and are also usually accompanied by members of the press/journalists so that the trade show is grouped as General or Trade Only. Through the trade show (expo), a form of the business matching expo, the hope is that business actors have sensitivity to market tastes strongly influenced by lifestyle, economy, society, and culture. Expertise in mastering and utilizing technology to produce quality products is also needed to increase the possibility of such products being accepted by global consumers and also to develop their business through investment (Handayani, 2022)

OBJECTIVES

The research objectives are: (a) Provide an overview of investment strategies for Bandung through business matching models; (b) Suitable business communication in attracting investors to the City of Bandung. The scope of research is limited to several aspects: studying investment strategies suitable for the City of Bandung and preparing Business Matching models.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Matching Concept

Matching is a natural (artificial) process involving interaction and best matching. The best way is associated with survival and deals with similar industrial and business matching processes, distributors, retailers, customers, jobs, and machines/computers (Moghaddam & Nof, 2017).

Matching is the process of business collaboration with other businesses, including suppliers, distributors, retailers, and customers. Through this collaboration, a company can establish a relationship of interrelationship and dependence in the business development framework and have sustainable competitiveness. Matching (adj) is conformity according to patterns, colors, or complementary designs. Matching (Ver) causes relatability in some crucial respects, which will make the relationship harmonious in quality or strength. The best matches occur when the goals business/community are following the benefits provided by other businesses that establish business relationships and when community assets follow business demands (Doughty, 2000).

Business Matching

Business matching is matching or adjusting ideas, concepts, visions and missions, and business models according to values, culture, and economic climate. Adjustment to business concepts is made between similar businesses with the same goals. Business matching and adjustment to the idea of business matching usually brings together entrepreneurs in a discussion sharing activity from entrepreneurs and startups with efforts to increase sustainable competitiveness (Moghaddam & Nof, 2017).

The development of new businesses needs a strategy to survive (survive) and good management. For beginner entrepreneurs, it takes a deeper exploration of what can be used to make a product or service better and of better quality. Business Matching is a strategic goal to collaborate with several businesses in one community in the business world. Business Matching is commonly more advanced and has sustainable durability (Crum & Palmatier, 2003).

Business collaboration can be very profitable for business actors. For example, businesses with online business cores, collaborating with MSMEs with quality, unique and distinctive local products, have wider business opportunities through online marketing. The official government website has listed MSMEs with various businesses in an area advanced with digital technology. There will be many benefits obtained by business matching collaboration. One advantage of business actors' matching concept is that MSMEs can reach the broader market. It is a business strategy that can make MSMEs able to compete (Kurniadi in Trehan & Trehan, 2022).

Business Matching Framework

Business Matching activities through fair trade / fair show or fair expo. Government / non-governmental agencies organizing fairtrade can strengthen B-to-B relationships. Business matching brings entrepreneurs, company leaders, MSME actors, newly grown startup actors, and investors from the Government, Banking, or the Private Sector. The business matching participants are delegates from agencies or companies from other countries. Fairtrade is expected to create sustainable competitiveness and increase macroeconomic growth that impacts the community's welfare (Yeow, 2000).

The role of the Government and non-governments such as the Chamber of Commerce and Industry usually only provide services as a forum to organize expo activities. To facilitate both parties of business actors to cooperate, if there is a cooperative relationship, the action is called matching in establishing business attachments (Baluch et al., 2015).

Providers of ease of trade, such as the Bandung City Investment Office and Integrated Services, must understand the scope of business relationships. Business relationships are an effort to connect stakeholders in a business meeting, including bonding Agents, Distributors, Suppliers; Marketing; Licensing; Contract; OEM, Private labels, Franchise; Joint research and development; Equity participation or investors; Joint venture; Mergers and acquisition (Kurniadi and & Ibrahim, 2021).

It is essential that this meeting is B2B and between two parties with match/same business industry backgrounds. Usually, the delegates will come in a group to find potential buyers(s) that match their business targets (Binar, 2015).

General Procedures of Business Matching

There are several levels of business matching. Figure 2 explains the business matching relationship to the needs of the required Resources role. Resources in this context are related agencies that become facilitators of business matching program organizers. In this research, the Bandung City Investment and Integrated Services Office, Bandung City Chamber of Commerce, and the Department of Industry and Trade have an essential role as organizers of fair trade fairs or trade expos as a form of business matching.

Source: (Yeow, 2000)

Figure 2. Scope of Business Matching Program

In figure 2, Information services on trade and business opportunities is a form of service provided in the form of information about trade and business opportunities for business actors. At this level, usually, the organizers of the business matching program can offer and implement it. Joint ventures, business collaborations, mergers, and acquisitions require high expertise legally, financially, and technically. So Joint ventures, business collaborations, unions, and investments are outside the scope of the role of the relevant agencies as the organizer of the business matching program.

METHODS

Location and time of research

This research was conducted in Bandung City, Indonesia. The work on the preparation of business matching planning is completed in 90 (Ninety) calendar days. The schedule for the implementation of this research is as follows;

Table 3. Business Matching Planning Schedule

No	Activities	1st month					2nd month					3rd month				
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
1	Preparation of research design															
2	Discussion of research design and data that is a reference															

No	Activities	1st month					2nd month					3rd month				
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
3	Data collection (literature study, research mapping & coordination)															
4	Discussion of research results															
5	FGD Research															
10	Publication of Research Results															

Data Collection Methods

This research uses a qualitative approach. The research aims to acquire understanding, develop concepts or theories, and describe the objects complexly under study (Amirudin & Asikin, 2006; Hasan, 2012). Data collection techniques use documentation methods (Soekanto, 1986).

Also, get data and information business matching, especially in the form of secondary data published by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), as a body or agency with the authority and credibility to present the data and information needed in Indonesia. Most secondary data refers to BPS. Then the data and information are sourced from the Bandung City Investment and Integrated Services Office, the Cooperative Office, SMEs and Trade Industry of B Bandung City, and the Bandung City Statistics Center Agency.

Then data and information from literature studies were sourced from online electronic library databases, e-books, trusted online journal databases, scientific open access journals, and books to conference proceedings results. Searching literature refers to Petersen et al. (2009) and Kitchenham (2007), a database search using keywords; "Business Matching" AND Trade.

Literature searches are carried out on the database mentioned above. Search results of some of the literature that has been studied are selected manually following the study so that the data obtained can be relevant to this research. Table 4 shows the results of exorcism literature from electronic database searches:

Table 4. Results of Penelusuran Literature on Business Matching

No	Database	Search Date	Search String	Doc. Type	Detected	Inclusion	Exclusion	Percentage
1	Scopus	November 2017	("Business Matching" AND Trade)	Journal	3	1	2	33.33%
2	ProQuest Research Library	November 2017	("Business Matching" AND Trade)	Journal	6	1	5	17%
3	Science Direct	November 2017	("Business Matching" AND Trade)	Journal	24	4	20	16.67%
4	Springer	November 2017	("Business Matching" AND Trade)	Journal	2		2	0.00%
5	Emerald Insight	November 2017	("Business Matching" AND Trade)	Journal	4			0.00%
Total Searches					39	6	29	15.38%

Data Analysis Methods

In a qualitative approach, data analysis uses deductive methods used in discussion, departing from knowledge of a general nature and then assessing something of a unique character. The general understanding in this study refers to the analysis of literature on business matching, fair trade, fair show/expo, and related about invertase and capital (Hadi, 1989). Thus, after departing from the general concept that has been generalized, then interpreted with existing theories and reference sources, the result is strategic business matching models to bring inventiveness that can be implemented in the city of Bandung.

RESULTS

Population Growth Rate in Bandung City

Table 5. Population Growth Rate of Bandung City

Year	Population	Rate of Population Growth per Year
2016	2,429,176	0.71
2017	2,444,617	0.64
2018	2,458,503	0.57
2019	2,470,802	0.50
2020	2,481,469	0.43
2021	2,490,622	0.37

Source: Research Results (2021)

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Table 6. Number of Small and Medium Industrial Units in West Java

Regency/ City	Business Unit	Workforce	Investment	Business Unit	Workforce	Investment
	2018			2019		
Bandung	12,269	123,812	450,671,15	13,473	188,855	1,111,471,29
Sumedang	5,030	103,540	42,408,90	5,130	159,477	57,508,9
West Bandung	16	480	14,980,00	17	1,680	69,980
Bandung	10,701	72,431	69,253,40	10,820	121,120	147,980,4
Cimahi City	6,028	109,267	31,573,95	6,097	187,215	599,124,66
West Java	198,478	2,280,375	6,040,433,20	203,060	4,216,671	130,681,582,73

Table 7. Number of Small and Medium Industrial Units in West Java advanced

Regency/ City	Business Unit	Workforce	Investment	Business Unit	Workforce	Investment
	2000			2021		
Bandung	13,483	189,850	1,121,566,29	13,483	189,850	1,121,566,29
Sumedang	5,130	159,477	4,960,586,9	5,130	159,477	4,960,586,90
West Bandung	52	2,251	5,764,877,6	52	2,251	5,764,877,60
Bandung	10,820	121,120	8,560,783,48	10,821	121,120	8,560,783,48

Regency/ City	Business Unit	Workforce	Investment	Business Unit	Workforce	Investment
	2000			2021		
Cimahi City	6,112	187,215	3,068,699,06	6,112	187,215	3,068,699,06
West Java	203,312	4,221,285	212,529,635,83	203,419	4,221,393	213,076,638,83

Source: Research Results (2021)

Data on Realization of Major Commodity Exports in Bandung City 2016

Table 8. Realization of Major Commodity exports in Bandung City 2016

Types of Commodities	Volume	Value
Electronic Devices	-	-
Medical Devices	6,047,293,20	11,115,811,87
Household Appliances	-	-
Musical instrument	-	-
Labatorium Tool	-	-
Furniture	194,492,10	3,220,246,77
Gondorukem /Terpentine	-	-
Rubber / Rubber Products	3,079,776,30	4,014,718,77
Skin / Skin Products	-	-
Marble / Ceramic	1,484,531,20	5,765,848,32
Rugs / Carpets	148,333,759,72	20,295,301,81
Drugs	1,857,581,09	14,946,826,50
Textiles / Textile Products	52,056,637,58	238,650,294,15
Tea		-
Apparel	88,948,255,78	200,806,592,33
Thread	30,382,571,63	58,486,839,80
Tricycle	186,978,60	5,593,068,89

Source: Research Results (2021)

DISCUSSION

Overview of Investment Opportunities in Bandung City

Bandung City contributes to national economic growth. The role of the financial sector is illustrated by the economic contribution of West Java province. The economic structure of Bandung City is service sector dominant.

Source: Research Results (2021)

Figure 3. Bandung Economic Structure 2015-2021

In the Large Trade and Retail Sector, Car and Motorcycle Repair became the most dominant sector in Bandung, between 2010-2016, with an average contribution of 28.16%. The sector that contributed the second largest was the Processing Industry Sector which contributed 22.41%. These two sectors account for half of the economic activity in the city of Bandung. Information Sector (Communication), Construction Sector, and Transportation Sector (Trade), contributing about 26%. The five sectors contribute about 76% of economic activity in the Bandung. The attractive economic structure in Bandung is among the various service sectors that dominate, and there is still the Processing Industry Sector as a real sector that still survives in the city of Bandung. The Construction sector's existence is related to economic growth and population growth.

The economic structure of Bandung has potential for investors, capital investment, and business stakeholders and should prioritize as their target market. The realization of investment strategy and activities in the city of Bandung can be realized through a face-to-face method, namely with the Business Matching model.

The strategic role of Business Matching

Business matching is a strategic program to realize sustainable competitiveness. We formulated three reasons why we should go through business matching; (1) To expand the business network (networking). Many domestic entrepreneurs have difficulty getting the opportunity to grow their business because of the limitations of acquaintances and experience; (2) To streamline time and cost. At trade shows (expos), business actors can save time and costs in establishing business work. Business stakeholders can visit potential partners from various business models, countries, and industries in just a few hours without incurring such a high cost. So far, the constraints of business actors are limited information because the scope of business is so globally; and (3) To increase knowledge of business and trade trends that exist in the world globally. Because all business actors at the business matching expo display their products with various

innovations and creative new ideas, this is an opportunity for other business actors to innovate through business matching as a competitive means.

Business Matching Types

There are many business matching exhibitions held in Indonesia. Such as The Indonesian Chamber of Commerce and Industry, IBDexpo Indonesia, Trade Expo Indonesia, Fortune PR, Business Matching-Megabuild Expo, Indonesia Maritime Expo, P.T. Omni eComm Expo-Cvent. The Government also acts as the organizer of business matching expos, such as the Ministry of Trade, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Indonesia, and the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs, for Bandung through the Bandung City Investment and Integrated Services Office.

Government agencies or related private parties are expected to be able to bring together delegates and potential buyers from the city of Bandung. The challenge is the ignorance of Indonesian entrepreneurs regarding business models such as Business Matching, so need consultant's high persuasive ability and willingness to socialize directly with the "market" are needed. In addition, good relations with associations will significantly help attract more potential buyers (Kurniadi & Ibrahim, 2021).

Business matching aims to help Industries, MSMEs, and creative economy business actors forge strategic business partnerships and networks with Large Companies that will ultimately contribute to the country's wealth. The models used in the implementation of business matching are as follows:

Source: Kurniadi & Ibrahim, (2021)

Figure 4. Business Matching Model

Figure 4 is a business matching model carried out by Pack Africa's private organization (2017). Pack Africa is the 3rd International Exhibition for Packaging, Packaging, Food and Bread Industry in Egypt, Africa, and the Middle East. Pack Africa strives to match (match) delegate participants (visitors) with exhibitors who have what is needed by visitors. The delegate meets the exhibitors who produce a match called Matching (PackAfrica, 2017).

The organizers designed a model for the business matching program in line with the purpose and purpose of the expo activity itself. The SMIDEX exhibition was organized by a collaboration between the Malaysian Government and SMEcorp Malaysia from 15-17 November 2017. It is a business matching trade show (expo) that facilitates industries, SMEs, large companies, and even multi-national companies to display and offer the latest products, services, and technologies for the global market (SMIDEX, 2017)

Source: SME Corp. Malaysia (2017)

Figure 5. Business Matching Session on SMIDEX

First, the organizers provide helpful information for exhibitors. There was a face-to-face meeting between two business actors in business matching activities. Finally, form a new business partnership if the two match. Then after establishing a business partnership, the more prominent investor/agent/business actor improvised more deeply by talking about technical business details that will involve many distribution networks. It is called a direct discussion with business partners (suppliers, distributors, customers) before making a decision (making a decision) at one by one meeting. After a series of models above, the last is a final transaction such as signing an MoU.

The business matching session activities above provide a new view of how business matching sessions are carried out and run. Investors will be more interested in the business matching session as displaying strategic data related to industries, MSMEs, and the creative economy where business matching exhibitions are held.

Business Matching Procedures

In general, the official business meeting procedure usually begins with an introductory session or the process of exchanging business cards (personal business information). It continued with product explanations, then discussions to produce business decisions. According to Binar (2017), to be conducive and efficient, usually, every meeting will be limited to 10 to 20 minutes in a private atmosphere. The total number of business delegates present from abroad usually amounts to 7 to 10 delegates. Simultaneously, representatives from abroad hope to get partners who can market their products in Indonesia. If the discussion goes smoothly, there will be a business partnership agreement through the signing a Memorium of Understanding (MOU) directly by both parties.

There are several stages through the role of the organizer's institution, precisely the business matching procedure. This point refers to Ho (2017), released at the old Exporthelp Asia. The stages of business matching are explained in the graphic scheme, which includes:

Source: Yeow, 2000; Ho, 2017

Figure 6. Business Matching Procedures

The above scheme is a procedure that explains the stages of business matching activities at a trade show held by both the Government and the private sector. Every action in business matching is strongly emphasized and must be documented and archived because the information data of cooperation activities affect economic growth in one region. In the city of Bandung, looking at the pace of economic growth is very potential to formulate agendas planning business matching activities.

CONCLUSION

- a) The dominant economic sectors in the Bandung city are the Large Trade and Retail Industry and the Processing Industry. The processing Industry built in the past is increasingly declining competitiveness. According to population growth and urban characteristics, the Trade sector tends to be flexible.
- b) The economic structure in Bandung has such great potential for business development and makes the company able to compete in global and sustainable competitions for Business Agents; Distributor; Supplier; Marketing; Licensing; Contract; OEMs; Private labels; Franchise; Joint R&D; Public and Private Equity or Investors; Joint venture; Mergers and acquisitions, both from abroad and from within the country.
- c) Support for the realization of investment activities in Bandung can be realized through Business Matching, which is a face-to-face method. Through face-to-face methods, it will accelerate business decision-making through in-depth discussion. In the end, business matching held will produce output in MoU or business contracts. Furthermore, it will form cooperation in the form of business collaboration.
- d) The limitations of literature and references make obstacles for the organizers because they are activities that can be measured. Models and stages must be used as references for business matching organizers in trade shows or expo activities.

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